

Whole-genome sequences of epiphytic *Bacillus* strains with biocontrol potentialities against the bacterial phytopathogen *Erwinia amylovora*

Olfa Frikha-Gargouri^{a*}, Dorra Ben Abdallah^{a,b}

^a Laboratory of Biopesticides, Centre of Biotechnology of Sfax, Sfax University, P.O. Box 1177, 3018 Sfax, Tunisia.

^b Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Monastir, University of Monastir, Avenue Taher Hadded (B.P 74), 5000, Monastir, Tunisia.

***Corresponding author:** Olfa Frikha-Gargouri, Biopesticides laboratory, Centre of Biotechnology of Sfax, Sfax University, P.O. Box “1177” 3018, Sfax, Tunisia.

Tel. /Fax: 0021626672789

E-mail address: olfafrikhagargouri2@gmail.com, olfa.frikhagargouri@cbs.rnrt.tn

Abstract

This study reports the complete and annotated genome assemblies of two epiphytic strains originating from pear and apple trees: *Peribacillus frigoritolerans* P.F1 and *Bacillus paralicheniformis* PF12. These strains exhibit antibacterial activities against *Erwinia amylovora*. Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) was used for sequencing which is a valuable strategy to characterize *Bacillus* strains and provides insights into biocontrol mechanisms.

Introduction

Fire blight is a highly destructive bacterial disease caused by *Erwinia amylovora*. This disease poses a significant threat to apple and pear tree cultivation, resulting in substantial economic losses for growers worldwide (Chen et al., 2009). In 2012, this devastating pathogen made its first appearance in pear plantations in Tunisia. It rapidly disseminates throughout major pear fruit production regions affecting consequently several hundred hectares (Gaaliche et al., 2018). Despite efforts through the various control measures to contain the disease, their effectiveness has been limited. Consequently, the need for novel strategies to manage fire blight is urgent. One of the promising methods for disease control is the biological control using beneficial microorganisms, of which Gram-positive *Bacillus* and *Bacillus*-related species emerged as attractive candidates. These spore-forming bacteria are highly used as biopesticides due to their extended shelf life (Jallouli et al., 2020; Miljaković et al., 2020). In addition,

Bacillus species are prevalent in diverse environments, enabling them to adapt and persist under varying conditions. These properties, along with their capacity to produce a wide range of biologically active compounds, explain their dominance as microbial products available for phytosanitary applications.

Bacillus-based products marketed and applied for fire blight control have shown inconsistent disease suppression rates varying from 71% to 0% (Chen et al., 2009). In our previous study, we reported the isolation and use of epiphytic *Bacillus* and *Bacillus*-derived strains from apple and pear plants as biocontrol agents against fire blight disease (Abdallah et al., 2023). These strains were isolated from the location where *E. amylovora* infects the plant. Therefore, these strains might perform well, since they could persist in the local environment and outcompete with indigenous bacteria and the phytopathogen which likely contribute to their efficacy. In this study, we report the WGS data of two epiphytic strains *Peribacillus frigoritolerans* P.F1 and *Bacillus paralicheniformis* PF12. These strains were selected for their antibacterial activities *in situ* against *E. amylovora* (Abdallah et al., 2023).

Material and Methods

Bacterial isolates

P. frigoritolerans P.F1 and *B. paralicheniformis* PF12 strains were isolated from epiphytic aerial parts of pear and apple trees in Sfax, Tunisia (Abdallah et al., 2023).

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

Bacteria were prepared following MicrobesNG strain submission procedures. DNA processing was conducted by MicrobesNG. DNA quantification and library preparation were carried out on a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland). Genomic DNA libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol with the following modifications: the amount of input DNA was increased 2-fold, and the PCR elongation time was increased to 45 seconds. Libraries were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired-end protocol.

The reads were adapter trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. *De novo* assembly was performed on samples using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012), and contigs were annotated using Prokka 1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Results

Genomic Features

A summary of the genomic features for *P. frigorigerans* P.F1 and *B. paralicheniformis* PF12 is listed in table 1. Genome assemblies were 5.5 and 4.3 Mb with 44 and 81 × mean coverage, respectively. The number of protein coding genes for *P. frigorigerans* P.F1 was 5325 genes; however, 4296 genes were predicted for *B. paralicheniformis* PF12. The G + C contents of *P. frigorigerans* P.F1 and *B. paralicheniformis* PF12 were 40.6 % and 45.9 %, respectively.

Nucleotides sequences accession numbers

The *P. frigorigerans* P.F1 and *B. paralicheniformis* PF12 complete genome sequences have been deposited in the NCBI GenBank under accession numbers listed in table 1.

Table1: Genomic features of *P. frigorigerans* P.F1 and *B. paralicheniformis* PF12

Bacterial species	<i>P. frigorigerans</i>	<i>B. paralicheniformis</i>
Strain	P.F1	PF12
Genome size (bp)	5517973	4332684
% GC	40.58	45.89
Number of contigs (>=1000 bp)	78	18
Largest contig (bp)	335256	1100144
Mean coverage (X)	43.8596	80.6303
Number of reads	500902	748790
N50 (bp)	139469	643228
Protein-coding gene	5325	4296
tRNA number	83	82
tmRNA number	1	1
SRA accession numbers	SRR27241192	SRR27386914
Assemblies accession numbers	GCA_034718975.1	GCA_035282705.1

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are being made available before their formal publication and should be considered as preliminary. We welcome feedback from the community. For further information, please contact OFG (olfafrikhagargouri2@gmail.com).

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